
LOCAL DIFFERENCES DETERMINED BY CONVEX SETS

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Abstract

This paper introduces a new problem concerning additive properties of convex sets. Let $S = \{s_1 < \dots < s_n\}$ be a set of real numbers and let $D_i(S) = \{s_x - s_y : 1 \leq x - y \leq i\}$. We expect that $D_i(S)$ is large, with respect to the size of S and the parameter i , for any convex set S . We give a construction to show that $D_3(S)$ can be as small as $n + 2$, and show that this is the smallest possible size. On the other hand, we use an elementary argument to prove a non-trivial lower bound for $D_4(S)$, namely $|D_4(S)| \geq \frac{5}{4}n - 1$. For sufficiently large values of i , we are able to prove a non-trivial bound that grows with i using incidence geometry.

1. Introduction

Let $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a finite set and write $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ such that $s_i < s_{i+1}$ for all $i \in [n - 1]$. S is said to be a *convex set* if $s_{i+1} - s_i < s_{i+2} - s_{i+1}$ for all $i \in [n - 2]$.

In the spirit of the sum-product problem, Erdős raised the question of whether $A + A$ and $A - A$ are guaranteed to be large for any convex set. Progress has been made towards this question via a combination of methods in incidence geometry (see for instance [2]) and elementary methods (see [3], [8] and [4]), but the question of determining the best possible lower bounds remains open. The current state-of-the-art results state that, for some absolute constant $c > 0$, the bounds

$$|S - S| \gg \frac{n^{8/5}}{(\log n)^c}, \quad |S + S| \gg \frac{n^{30/19}}{(\log n)^c} \quad (1)$$

hold for any convex set $A \subset \mathbb{R}$, see [10] and [7] respectively. The notation \gg is used to absorb a multiplicative constant. That is $X \gg Y$ denotes that there exists an absolute constant $C > 0$ such that $X \geq CY$.

In this paper, we introduce a new *local* variant of this problem, where only differences between close elements of A are considered. We define

$$D_i(S) := \{s_x - s_y : 1 \leq x - y \leq i\}.$$

Moreover, for any set $\mathcal{I} \subset [n - 1]$, define

$$D_{\mathcal{I}}(S) := \{s_x - s_y \mid x - y \in \mathcal{I}\}.$$

We expect that $D_i(S)$ is large (in terms of i) and that $D_{\mathcal{I}}(S)$ is large (in terms of $|\mathcal{I}|$) for any convex set $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. We begin with some trivial observations.

- For any convex set S , $|D_1(S)| = |S| - 1$. Indeed, it is an immediate consequence of the definition of a convex set that S has *distinct consecutive differences*. Additive properties of such sets were considered in [8] and [9].
- For any convex set S , we have $|D_2(S)| \geq |S|$. This can be seen by observing that $s_n - s_{n-2} \in D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)$, and so

$$|D_2(S)| = |D_{\{1\}}(S)| + |D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)| \geq n - 1 + 1 = n. \tag{2}$$

On the other hand, if we consider the set

$$S = \{f_{i+3} : i \in [n]\}, \tag{3}$$

where f_i is the i -th Fibonacci number, we see that $|D_2(S)| = n$, and so the lower bound (2) is optimal.

- Setting $i = n - 1$, we see that the set $D_i(S)$ is equal to the set of positive elements of the difference set $S - S$. Therefore, the question of obtaining lower bounds for $D_{n-1}(S)$ is equivalent to that of lower bounding the size of $S - S$.

The main results of this paper concern the minimum possible sizes of $D_3(S)$ and $D_4(S)$ when S is convex. Let $\mathcal{S}(n)$ be the set of all convex sets of size n . Define

$$D_i(n) := \min\{|D_i(S)| : S \in \mathcal{S}(n)\}.$$

The discussion above shows that $D_1(n) = n - 1$ and $D_2(n) = n$. For $D_3(n)$ we will provide a constructive proof of the following result.

Theorem 1.1. *For any integer $n \geq 5$,*

$$D_3(n) = n + 2.$$

However, there is an interesting change of behaviour that occurs when i goes from 3 to 4, and $D_4(n)$ is not of the form $n + O(1)$. In this paper we will prove the following result.

Theorem 1.2. *For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$,*

$$D_4(n) \geq \frac{5}{4}n - 1.$$

We also consider a stronger notion of convexity, namely k -convexity, which was one of the main considerations of the paper [4].

Definition 1.3. A set S is k -convex if $D_1(S)$ is a $(k - 1)$ -convex set. A convex set is also called a 1-convex set.

Let $\mathcal{S}^2(n)$ be the set of all 2-convex sets of size n . Define

$$D_i^2(n) := \min\{|D_i(S)| : S \in \mathcal{S}^2(n)\}.$$

Note that $D_1^2(n) = n - 1$. The set S defined in (3) is a 2-convex set with $|D_2(S)| = n$, and it therefore follows that $D_2^2(n) = n$.

Similarly to Theorem 1.1 we will prove the following result.

Theorem 1.4. *For any integer $n \geq 5$,*

$$D_3^2(n) = n + 2. \tag{4}$$

We give a slightly better lower bound for $D_4^2(n)$ than that for $D_4(n)$ given in Theorem 1.2.

Theorem 1.5. *For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$,*

$$D_4^2(n) \geq \frac{4}{3}n - \frac{4}{3}.$$

We expect that the values of $D_i(n)$ and $D_i^2(n)$ increase with i , and it may even be possible that a lower bound of the form $\Omega((ni)^{1-\epsilon})$ holds. However, we are not able to generalize the elementary techniques used to prove Theorems 1.2 and 1.4 to obtain better bounds by considering larger i .

On the other hand, for sufficiently large i , a non-trivial lower bound for $D_i(n)$ can be obtained by a trivial application of the lower bound for $S - S$ in (1). Indeed, let S be a convex set with cardinality n and let $S' \subset S$ denote the subset formed by taking the i smallest elements. Then

$$|D_i(S)| \geq |D_i(S')| \gg |S' - S'| \gg \frac{i^{8/5}}{(\log n)^c} \tag{5}$$

In particular, if $i \geq n^{5/8+\epsilon}$, then (5) gives a lower bound of the form

$$D_i(n) \gg n^{1+\epsilon'}. \tag{6}$$

It appears plausible that (6) holds under the weaker assumption that $i \geq n^\epsilon$.

In this paper, we use incidence geometric techniques to give a more general result, see the forthcoming Theorem 2.1. In particular, this gives us a good lower bound for the size of $D_{\mathcal{I}}(S)$ when $|\mathcal{I}|$ is large.

2. Proofs of the Main Results

Proof of Theorems 1.1 and 1.4. To prove that $D_3(n) \geq n+2$, we need to prove that

$$|D_3(S)| \geq n+2 \tag{7}$$

holds for an arbitrary convex set S with $|S| = n$. Observe that $|D_3(S)| \geq |D_2(S)|+1$, since $s_n - s_{n-3} \in D_3(S) \setminus D_2(S)$. Hence $|D_3(S)| \geq n+1$. Suppose for a contradiction that $|D_3(S)| = n+1$ for some $n \geq 5$. Observe that

$$s_2 - s_1 < s_3 - s_2 < s_3 - s_1 < s_4 - s_2 < s_4 - s_1 < s_5 - s_2 < \dots < s_n - s_{n-3}$$

and

$$s_2 - s_1 < s_3 - s_2 < s_4 - s_3 < s_4 - s_2 < s_5 - s_3 < s_5 - s_2 < \dots < s_n - s_{n-3}.$$

We have identified two increasing sequences of length $n+1$ in $D_3(S)$, and so the sequences must be identical. Comparing the third terms of the sequences, we get

$$s_4 - s_3 = s_3 - s_1 \tag{8}$$

and comparing the fifth terms of the sequences, we get

$$s_4 - s_1 = s_5 - s_3. \tag{9}$$

From Equations (8) and (9) we get

$$s_5 - s_4 = s_3 - s_1 = s_4 - s_3.$$

But as S is a convex set this is not possible. Hence our assumption that $|D_3(S)| = n+1$ was wrong, and so $|D_3(S)| \geq n+2$, proving (7).

Since every 2-convex set is also convex, it follows that $|D_3(S)| \geq n+2$ for all 2-convex sets S . Therefore, $D_3^2(n) \geq n+2$.

To prove that $D_3(n) \leq n + 2$ and $D_3^2(n) \leq n + 2$, we provide an example of a 2-convex (and thus also convex) set with $|D_3(S)| = n + 2$. Consider the set $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ where

$$s_1 = 0, s_2 = 10, s_3 = 23, s_4 = 40,$$

$$s_i := s_{i-1} + s_{i-2} - s_{i-4} \text{ for } i = 5, \dots, n.$$

Indeed, $|D_3(S)| = n + 2$. Observe that

$$s_{i+5} - s_{i+4} = s_{i+2} - s_i \forall i \in [1, n - 5]. \tag{10}$$

We will prove that S is 2-convex by induction on n . The base case, with $n = 5, 6, 7$, can be checked by a direct calculation.

Now let $n \geq 8$. To show S is 2-convex it is sufficient to show that

$$(s_{i+3} - s_{i+2}) - (s_{i+2} - s_{i+1}) > (s_{i+2} - s_{i+1}) - (s_{i+1} - s_i) \tag{11}$$

for all $i \in [1, n - 3]$. We know from the induction hypothesis that (11) holds for $i = 1, \dots, n - 4$, and so we only need to check that it is valid for $i = n - 3$.

From Equation (10) we know that

$$(s_n - s_{n-1}) - (s_{n-1} - s_{n-2}) = (s_{n-3} - s_{n-5}) - (s_{n-4} - s_{n-6})$$

$$= (s_{n-3} - s_{n-4}) - (s_{n-5} - s_{n-6}). \tag{12}$$

Analogously,

$$(s_{n-1} - s_{n-2}) - (s_{n-2} - s_{n-3}) = (s_{n-4} - s_{n-5}) - (s_{n-6} - s_{n-7}). \tag{13}$$

Applying (11) twice (with $i = n - 6$ and $i = n - 7$), it follows that

$$(s_{n-3} - s_{n-4}) - (s_{n-4} - s_{n-5}) > (s_{n-5} - s_{n-6}) - (s_{n-6} - s_{n-7}).$$

Rearranging gives

$$(s_{n-3} - s_{n-4}) - (s_{n-5} - s_{n-6}) > (s_{n-4} - s_{n-5}) - (s_{n-6} - s_{n-7}).$$

We then apply (12) and (13) to conclude that

$$(s_n - s_{n-1}) - (s_{n-1} - s_{n-2}) > (s_{n-1} - s_{n-2}) - (s_{n-2} - s_{n-3}).$$

This proves (11) for the case $i = n - 3$, as required. □

Taking a closer look at the construction of the set S defined above, we see that there is additional structure, as the set $D_{\{5\}}(S)$ overlaps significantly with $D_3(S)$. To be precise, we have

$$|D_{\{1,2,3,5\}}(S)| = n + 4.$$

Since the two largest elements of $D_{\{1,2,3,5\}}(S)$ are not in $D_3(S)$, it follows from Theorem 1.1 that $D_{\{1,2,3,5\}}(S) \geq n + 4$ for any convex set S , and so this construction is optimal in this regard.

Proof of Theorem 1.2. To prove Theorem 1.2, we need to show that

$$|D_4(S)| \geq \frac{5}{4}n - 1 \tag{14}$$

holds for an arbitrary convex set S with size n . Indeed, let S be such a set. The proof of (14) is split into two cases.

Case 1. Suppose that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)| \geq \frac{n}{4} - 2$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |D_4(S)| &\geq |D_2(S)| + 2 = |D_{\{1\}}(S) \cup [D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)]| + 2 \\ &\geq (n - 1) + (n/4 - 2) + 2 = \frac{5n}{4} - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. Suppose that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)| < n/4 - 2$. It follows that

$$s_{i+2} - s_i, s_{i+3} - s_{i+1} \in D_{\{1\}}(S)$$

holds for at least

$$(n - 3) - 2(n/4 - 2) = \frac{n}{2} + 1$$

values of $i \in [n - 3]$. Let I be the set of all such i . Then, for all $i \in I$,

$$s_{i+2} - s_i = s_{j+1} - s_j, \quad s_{i+3} - s_{i+1} = s_{j'+1} - s_j,$$

for some $j, j' \in [n - 1]$.

Case 2a. Suppose that, for at least $\frac{n}{4} + 2$ of the elements $i \in I$, we have $j' = j + 1$. Then $s_{j+2} - s_j$ is in $D_{\{2\}}(S)$, but it is also strictly between two consecutive elements of $D_{\{4\}}(S)$. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} s_{i+3} - s_{i-1} &= (s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}) + (s_{i+1} - s_{i-1}) \\ &< (s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}) + (s_{i+2} - s_i) \\ &= (s_{j+2} - s_{j+1}) + (s_{j+1} - s_j) \\ &= s_{j+2} - s_j \\ &< (s_{i+4} - s_{i+2}) + (s_{i+2} - s_i) \\ &= s_{i+4} - s_i. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{4\}}(S)| \geq \frac{n}{4} + 2$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |D_4(S)| &\geq 1 + |D_{\{2,4\}}(S)| = 1 + |D_{\{4\}}(S) \cup [D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{4\}}(S)]| \\ &\geq 1 + n - 4 + \frac{n}{4} + 2 = \frac{5n}{4} - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2b. Suppose that we are not in case 2a, and hence, for at least $\frac{n}{4} - 1$ of the elements of I , we have $j' \geq j + 2$. Then $s_{j+2} - s_{j+1}$ lies strictly between

two consecutive elements of $D_{\{2\}}$, namely $s_{i+2} - s_i$ and $s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}$. Therefore, $|D_{\{1\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{2\}}(S)| \geq \frac{n}{4} - 1$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned} |D_4(S)| &\geq |D_2(S)| + 2 = |D_{\{2\}}(S) \cup [D_{\{1\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{2\}}(S)]| + 2 \\ &\geq (n - 2) + (n/4 - 1) + 2 = \frac{5n}{4} - 1. \end{aligned}$$

□

A closer look at the proof of Theorem 1.2 reveals that we have barely used the elements of $D_{\{3\}}(S)$ anywhere in the proof of (14). By modifying the proof slightly, we obtain the bound

$$|D_{\{1,2,4\}}(S)| \geq \frac{5}{4}n - 2$$

for any convex set S with cardinality n .

The construction of the set S from Theorem 1.1 yields the bound

$$|D_4(S)| \leq |D_3(S)| + (n - 4) = 2n - 2.$$

Combining this observation with the result of Theorem 1.2, we see that

$$\frac{5}{4}n - 1 \leq D_4(n) \leq 2n - 2.$$

We now proceed to the proof of Theorem 1.5. The proof is largely the same as that of Theorem 1.2. The main difference is that we can use the 2-convex condition to show that Case 2b does not occur.

Proof of Theorem 1.5. To prove Theorem 1.5, we need to show that

$$|D_4(S)| \geq \frac{4}{3}n - \frac{4}{3} \tag{15}$$

holds for an arbitrary 2-convex set S with size n . Indeed, let S be such a set. The proof is split into two cases.

Case 1. Suppose that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)| \geq \frac{n}{3} - \frac{7}{3}$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |D_4(S)| &\geq |D_2(S)| + 2 = |D_{\{1\}}(S) \cup [D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)]| + 2 \\ &\geq (n - 1) + \left(\frac{n}{3} - \frac{7}{3}\right) + 2 = \frac{4}{3}n - \frac{4}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. Suppose that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{1\}}(S)| < \frac{n}{3} - \frac{7}{3}$. It follows that

$$s_{i+2} - s_i, s_{i+3} - s_{i+1} \in D_{\{1\}}(S)$$

holds for at least

$$(n - 3) - 2 \left(\frac{n}{3} - \frac{7}{3}\right) = \frac{n}{3} + \frac{5}{3}$$

values of $i \in [n - 3]$. Let I be the set of all such i . Then, for all $i \in I$,

$$s_{i+2} - s_i = s_{j+1} - s_j, \quad s_{i+3} - s_{i+1} = s_{j'+1} - s_j,$$

for some $j, j' \in [n - 1]$ satisfying $j' > j > i$. We claim now that it must be the case that $j' = j + 1$. Indeed, suppose for a contradiction that $j' \geq j + 2$. It then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (s_{j+3} - s_{j+2}) - (s_{j+1} - s_j) &\leq (s_{j'+1} - s_{j'}) - (s_{j+1} - s_j) \\ &= (s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}) - (s_{i+2} - s_i) \\ &= (s_{i+3} - s_{i+2}) - (s_{i+1} - s_i). \end{aligned}$$

However, since $j > i$, this contradicts the assumption that S is 2-convex. Indeed, write the convex set $D_1(S) = \{d_1 < d_2 < \dots < d_{n-1}\}$, and so $d_i = s_{i+1} - s_i$. Then the previous inequality can be written as

$$d_{j+2} - d_j \leq d_{i+2} - d_i.$$

But this inequality cannot hold if $D_1(S)$ is convex, which proves the claim.

As was the case in the proof of Theorem 1.2, $s_{j+2} - s_j$ is in $D_{\{2\}}(S)$, but it is also strictly in-between two consecutive elements of $D_{\{4\}}(S)$. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} s_{i+3} - s_{i-1} &= (s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}) + (s_{i+1} - s_{i-1}) \\ &< (s_{i+3} - s_{i+1}) + (s_{i+2} - s_i) \\ &= (s_{j+2} - s_{j+1}) + (s_{j+1} - s_j) \\ &= s_{j+2} - s_j \\ &< (s_{i+4} - s_{i+2}) + (s_{i+2} - s_i) \\ &= s_{i+4} - s_i. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $|D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{4\}}(S)| \geq \frac{n}{3} + \frac{5}{3}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |D_4(S)| &\geq 1 + |D_{\{2,4\}}(S)| = 1 + |D_{\{4\}}(S) \cup [D_{\{2\}}(S) \setminus D_{\{4\}}(S)]| \\ &\geq 1 + n - 4 + \frac{n}{3} + \frac{5}{3} = \frac{4}{3}n - \frac{4}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

□

We now turn to the case of bounding $D_{\mathcal{I}}(S)$ for large \mathcal{I} , giving a modification of the proof of the main result in [2].

Theorem 2.1. *Let $S = \{s_1 < s_2 < \dots < s_n\}$ be convex and let $G \subset [n] \times [n]$. Then*

$$|\{s_x - s_y : (x, y) \in G\}| \gg \left(\frac{|G|}{n}\right)^{3/2}. \tag{16}$$

Similar sum-product type results for restricted pairs have been considered in, for instance, [1] and [5]. Note that the bound in (16) becomes meaningful when $|G|$ is significantly larger than n . A construction of a convex set with a rich difference in [6] shows that the set $\{s_x - s_y : (x, y) \in G\}$ can have cardinality as small as one when G has cardinality as large as $n/2$.

Proof of Theorem 2.1. We may assume that $|G| \geq 2n$, as otherwise the bound (16) becomes trivial since the right hand side of the inequality is constant.

Denote

$$S -_G S := \{s_x - s_y : (x, y) \in G\}.$$

We will prove that

$$|S -_G S| \gg \left(\frac{|G|}{n}\right)^{3/2}. \tag{17}$$

Since S is convex, it follows that there exists a strictly convex function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $f(i) = s_i$.

Define P to be the point set

$$P = \{-n, -n + 1, \dots, n - 1, n\} \times (S -_G S).$$

Let $\ell_{a,b}$ denote the curve with equation $y = f(x + a) - b$. Define L to be the set of curves

$$L = \{\ell_{j,s_h} : 1 \leq j, h \leq n\}.$$

The set L consists of translates of the same convex curve, and it therefore follows that we have the Szemerédi-Trotter type bound

$$I(P, L) \leq 4|P|^{2/3}|L|^{2/3} + 4|P| + |L|, \tag{18}$$

where

$$I(P, L) := \{(p, \ell) \in P \times L : p \in \ell\}.$$

For each $\ell_{j,s_h} \in L$, and for any k such that $(k, h) \in G$, observe that

$$(k - j, s_k - s_h) \in P \cap \ell_{j,s_h}.$$

This implies that

$$I(P, L) = \sum_{\ell \in L} |\ell \cap P| \geq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq n} \sum_{1 \leq h \leq n} |\{k : (k, h) \in G\}| = n|G|.$$

Comparing this bound with (18) yields

$$n|G| \leq 4n^2|S -_G S|^{2/3} + 4n|S -_G S| + n^2.$$

The assumption that $|G| \geq 2n$ can then be used to deduce that

$$n|G| \ll n^2|S -_G S|^{2/3} + n|S -_G S| \ll n^2|S -_G S|^{2/3},$$

where the latter inequality makes use of the (very) trivial bound $|S -_G S| \leq n^3$. A rearrangement gives the claimed bound (17). \square

3. Concluding Remarks

3.1. Sums Instead of Differences

One may also consider a version of this question with sums. Let $E_i(S)$ denote the set

$$E_i(S) = \{s_x + s_y : 1 \leq x - y \leq i\}.$$

However, it turns out that this modification to the question makes it rather straightforward to prove a non-trivial bound that grows with i . If we split S into disjoint consecutive blocks $S_1 \cup S_2 \cup \dots \cup S_t$, with each block having i elements (we possibly discard some elements to ensure that all blocks have exactly the same size, and so $t = \lfloor n/i \rfloor$), then the sum sets $S_j + S_j$ are pairwise disjoint. It then follows from the lower bound for $S_j + S_j$ given in (1) that

$$|S + S| \geq \sum_{j=1}^t |S_j + S_j| \gg \frac{n}{i} \cdot \frac{i^{30/19}}{(\log n)^c} = \frac{ni^{11/19}}{(\log n)^c}.$$

3.2. Sets \mathcal{I} such that $D_{\mathcal{I}} = n + O(1)$

In Theorem 1.1, we have seen that $D_{\{1,2,3\}}(n) = n + 2$. There are other examples of sets $\mathcal{I} \subset [n - 1]$ with cardinality 3 such that $D_{\mathcal{I}}(n) = n + O(1)$. For example, we can define S using the recurrence relation

$$s_n = s_{n-2} + s_{n-3} - s_{n-6}.$$

By choosing the initial elements of S suitably, the set S is convex. However, this recurrence relations gives rise to the system of equations

$$s_j - s_{j-2} = s_{j-3} - s_{j-6} = s_{j-5} - s_{j-9}, \quad \forall 10 \leq j \leq n.$$

This implies that the elements of $D_{\{2\}}(S), D_{\{3\}}(S)$ and $D_{\{4\}}(S)$ are largely the same, with just a few exceptions occurring at the extremes of the three sets. It follows that $D_{\{2,3,4\}}(S) = n + C$, for some absolute constant C . It appears likely that the same argument can be used to show that $D_{\{k,k+d,k+2d\}}(n) = n + O_{k,d}(1)$.

On the other hand, we have seen in this paper that $D_{\{1,2,4\}}(n) = \frac{5n}{4} - O(1)$. This raises the following question: can we classify the sets \mathcal{I} with cardinality 3 with the property that $D_{\mathcal{I}}(n) = n + C$, where C is some constant (which may depend on the elements of \mathcal{I})?

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